

Inducing Suction Sensation by Positive Pressure Stimuli on the Palm

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Abstract. This study investigates a suction illusion where a decrease in positive pressure on the palm elicits a pulling sensation. Experiments using a custom tactile device revealed that a greater shell curvature and a larger indenter diameter intensify the effect. It was also revealed that the effect was intensified with a longer pressure period.

Keywords: Palm · Pulling sensation · Suction sensation · Haptic illusion

1 Introduction

Conventional haptic devices require grounding to support reaction forces, making them unsuitable for immersive VR environments. To achieve non-grounded rendering, various methods have been proposed, such as utilizing the gyro effect [1, 2] or asymmetric vibrations [3, 4]. Other approaches utilize haptic illusions [5, 6], where cutaneous cues trigger force perception in the absence of physical force. The palm is an ideal location to provide such cutaneous cues, since the palm is often in contact with VR controllers. Previous studies reported that pressurizing the palm can elicit a force sensation, but the elicited force was limited to the pushing direction [7, 8]. For practical applications, a pulling sensation should also be induced, but it is difficult to apply negative pressure on the palm with simple device structures.

To address this issue, this study reports on a suction illusion, where a user feels a sensation of being pulled. In this illusion, a user’s palm is only pushed by a device. Then, the user feels suction when the pushing force is released. The experiments of this paper reveal the physical conditions that are necessary for the emergence of this suction illusion. The experimental protocol was approved by the ethics committee of the University of Tokyo (E2025ALS065).

2 Stimulation device

To reveal the conditions for the emergence of the illusion, a dedicated device was developed, as shown in Fig. 1 (a). The device has a 3D-printed shell with a hole at its tip. The user places their hand to cover the hole with a contact force of approximately 10 N. Inside the shell, a voice coil motor (VCM) (Technohands,

Fig. 1. Overview of the device. (a) Hand placement and disassembled view showing the VCM-driven indenter and a shell. (b) Interchangeable shells (curvatures $r=50, 75, \infty$) and indenters with varying diameters.

AVM40-20, force coefficient: 13.6 N/A) was installed, with a 3D-printed indenter attached to its moving part. When actuated, the indenter protrudes through the shell’s hole to pressurize the palm.

For comparison, three cylindrical shells, all with a diameter of 100 mm, and four indenters with different diameters were prepared, as shown in Fig. 1 (b). The radii of curvature of the shells were 50 mm, 75 mm, and infinity, respectively. They all had a hole with a diameter of 35 mm at the center. All the four indenters had the same curvature at their ends (50 mm radius of curvature), but they differed in diameter: 10, 17, 25, and 32 mm. The shell and the stationary part of the VCM were fixed to a load cell to allow the user to regulate the contact force. The VCM was current-controlled by using a bipolar amplifier.

3 Experiments

To identify the optimal physical conditions for the suction illusion, we tested 12 combinations of the three shell curvatures and the four indenter diameters. A constant positive pressure (VCM driving current of 0.3 A) was applied for 3 seconds, after which the pressure was linearly decreased to zero over 3 seconds. Five male participants (ages: 21-23) rated the perceived suction strength on a 1-5 Likert scale (1: No sensation, 3: Weakly felt, 5: Clearly felt). Figure 2 (a) shows the results. The shells with smaller radii of curvature more effectively elicited the suction illusion. The illusion was hardly perceived when the shell was flat. These results suggest that the skin tension of the palm plays a crucial role. When contacting a curved surface, the palm skin better conforms to the shell curvature, resulting in lower initial tension, whereas it is stretched when contacting a flat surface. Since stretched skin resists deformation under pressure, this lack of deformation may explain the non-occurrence of the suction illusion. While the larger indenter was more effective, this may be due to either the larger contact area or the narrower gap with the edge of the shell hole.

Figure 2 (b) shows the results of another experiment, in which the time duration of the positive pressure (0.4 A for VCM) was varied. The positive pressure was applied for 0, 1, 3, and 5 seconds, after which the pressure was linearly

Fig. 2. Mean subjective ratings of suction illusion strength for (a) various combinations of shell radii and indenter diameters and for (b) different durations of the positive pressure. Error bars indicate standard errors.

decreased to zero over 1 second. Nine male participants (ages: 21-26) evaluated the suction sensation on an 11-level scale (0-10), with level 7 being the strength of the standard stimulus, which was presented to the participants before the experiments using vacuum suction; this scale was adopted to enable a quantitative comparison of intensity. Significant differences were observed between shorter pushing durations (0 and 1 s) and the longer durations (3 and 5 s). The results suggest that a longer duration increases the suction feeling, but it tends to saturate for durations longer than 3 seconds. This suggests that the illusion is likely driven by tactile aftereffects of the sustained pressure; previous studies revealed that tactile aftereffects could saturate after 2 seconds [9].

4 Conclusions

This study shows that a suction illusion can be elicited by pushing-based cutaneous stimulation on the palm. Key factors for a strong illusion include a curved shell geometry and extended pressure application time, suggesting that skin tension relaxation and tactile aftereffects are critical mechanisms. This phenomenon addresses the unidirectional limitation of the pseudo-force illusion using the normal pressure, enabling bidirectional force rendering in non-grounded devices.

Open Research Question and Interdisciplinary Exchange The size and variation of the participants were limited in this work, which should be expanded to confirm the universality of the illusion. Also, the effect of the stimulator shapes and the temporal pattern of the stimulation should be investigated extensively to better understand the underlying mechanism. As an interdisciplinary exchange, suitable applications for this haptic illusion should be explored across various fields.

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